

Cakawi [sic] Cam 1969

also known as “Thun Nâsak Mânuk Hâk”, “Sakawi Cam”, “Sakawi Cam : Thun nâsak mânuk hâk”

By William Noseworthy, Cornell University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Southeast Asian Religions, Text, Cosmology, Islamic Traditions, Southeast Asian Hinduism, Indic Religion, Canonical texts, Religious Holidays, Calendar, Malayo-Sumbawan, North and East Malayo-Sumbawan, Aceh-Chamic, Malayo-Polynesian, Austronesian, Language, Chamic, Coastal Chamic, Cham, Eastern Cham

This is a version of the Cham calendar and an introductory text produced for the 1969 calendar year of the Gregorian calendar by Ja Mâta Hârei. The text includes a translation of the original Cham introduction in English and Vietnamese. The calendar itself is written entirely in the Eastern Cham script of Akhar Thrah. The Cham calendar itself is a lunisolar calendar comprised of both Hindu and Muslim elements. It is presumed that the calendar was produced sometime in 1968. Because of the overlapping nature of lunisolar elements, the calendar implicitly covers portions of the Gregorian calendar year of 1970.

Date Range: 1968 CE - 1970 CE

Region: Sakawi Cam 20th century

Region tags: Southeast Asia, Bình Thuận, Bình Tuy, Vietnam, Ninh Thuận

This region covers the proximate regions of communities that would have closely followed the Sakawi Cam in the 20th century. The larger polygon corresponds to the area of indigenous Cham communities in the antiquated Republic of Vietnam provinces of Ninh Thuận, Bình Thuận, and Bình Tuy. In 1976 these three provinces were combined into the province of Thuận Hải (now: Ninh Thuận and Bình Thuận provinces, as of a 1992 split). Today's Ninh Thuận and Bình Thuận provinces correspond closely to the historical boundaries of Ninh Thuận, Bình Thuận and Bình Tuy in 1969. Cham people from this area have sometimes been referred to as "Panduranga Cham" as the region corresponds closely to the historical Cham kingdom of Panduranga. The smaller polygon to the southwest corresponds to the urban area of Saigon and outlying suburban developments. Some members of the Panduranga Cham community began to move to Saigon in increasing numbers after World War II. Although Saigon was renamed Hồ Chí Minh City in 1976 and additional land outside the original city has been since annexed to enlarge the municipality, the settlement areas for urban and suburban dwellers remain roughly within the same neighborhoods. Finally, the "Cakawi Cam" by Ja Mâta Hârei was

initially held in the Viện Chuyên-Khảo Ngữ-Học (Summer Institute of Linguistics) in what was then Saigon, as of the early 1970s.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Lịch pháp của người Chăm by Sakaya (Trí Thức, Hà Nội, 2016)
- Source 2: Sakawi Cam (Photographed during fieldwork, 2013-2014)

Notes: The first print source is a source that was published well after the text in reference, but is a good Vietnamese language source for understanding this genre of text. The second source is a manuscript that was photographed during fieldwork in 2013-2014 and is simply a similar version of the Cham calendar, albeit mapped for extended reference across multiple years.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A60726#page/8/mode/1up>
- Source 1 Description: This text is an example of a Sakawi Cam (Cham calendar) text from a 1978 version of a manuscript that was presumably copied and expounded upon from a previous version of the Cham calendar.
- Source 2 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A510#page/6/mode/1up>
- Source 2 Description: This manuscript represents an early 20th century version of the Ahiér (Hindu) elements of the Cham calendar and how to calculate, as well as interpret, elements of the calendar. It represents an example text of the material upon which Ja Mâta Hârei's calendar was likely based.
- Source 3 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A3974#page/8/mode/1up>
- Source 3 Description: This manuscript represents a late 19th or early 20th century commentary on the Cham calendar. It illustrates how the Ahiér (Hindu) elements of the calendar would have been interpreted in the early years of Ja Mâta Hârei's life.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1890 CE - 1978 CE

- Source 1 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A65748#page/12/mode/1up>
- Source 1 Description: This is a similar calendar for the Gregorian year 1980. It is an original manuscript that has both the Ahiér (Hindu) and Awal (Islamic) calendar systems.
- Source 2 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A64403#page/8/mode/1up>
- Source 2 Description: This is a similar calendar for the Gregorian year 1994. It is an original manuscript that has both the Ahiér (Hindu) and Awal (Islamic) calendar systems. However, it also shows some commentary on calculating the Islamic system.
- Source 3 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A63066#page/15/mode/1up>

– Source 3 Description: This text is a virtually contemporaneous commentary on the Cham calendar and systematization of social principles derived from the cosmology the calendar asserts. Notably, this version includes both Awal and Ahiér elements, as well as a few trace examples of Vietnamese language notes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1994 CE

– Source 1 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3A67621#page/3/mode/1up>

– Source 1 Description: This text is an early 20th century (French colonial era, pre-1954) text describing how to calculate the dates of the Cham calendar. Although the text is almost entirely in Akhar Thrah, and therefore might be presumed to only refer to the "Ahier" or Hindu elements of the calendar, the first line refers to al-Mâhâram (Muḥarram, الْمُحَرَّم) meaning the first month of the Islamic calendar is indeed the first point of reference.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1900 CE - 1954 CE

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://sea.lib.niu.edu/islandora/object/seadl%3Aacham>

– Source 1 Description: This link provides a porthole to access the Endangered Cham Manuscripts of Vietnam archived manuscripts as housed via the Southeast Asia Digital Library.

– Source 2 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/project/EAP531>

– Source 2 Description: This link provides an access point for the first Endangered Cham Manuscripts of Vietnam project, consisting of four sample manuscripts.

– Source 3 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/project/EAP698>

– Source 3 Description: This link provides an access point for the second Endangered Cham Manuscripts of Vietnam project, consisting of 529 sample manuscripts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2010 CE

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/project/EAP1005>

– Source 1 Description: This is a follow up 2017 project that digitized 497 sample manuscripts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2010 CE

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

↳ Number of sheets

– Bound

Notes: The typed version of this manuscript is bound in a single volume of 15 sheets that were printed originally in a mix of handwritten Cham Akhar Thrah script and also typed on typewriters. Although there was a Cham script typewriter available in this era, it does not appear to have been used for this manuscript. A typical romanized (French) keyboard, with diacritics, appears to have been used for the romanized Cham, Vietnamese, and English language text introductions.

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: A form of mid-century typewriter paper, relatively stiff, potentially manila paper or a manila paper mixed pulp composite.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

– Other [specify]: Translation and transliteration

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– Yes

Notes: In the occurrence that a scholar of the Cham community is buried, they might be interred with their manuscripts, including versions of the Cham calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2023 CE

– No

Notes: This specific version of the Cham calendar, to my knowledge, has not been buried with any individual.

↳ Cemetery

– Yes

Notes: Although members of the Cham Ahiér community are not typically buried in cemeteries, members of the Cham Bani community are. Consequently, versions of the Cham calendar might end up in those graves. However, this is not a likely occurrence, given the circumstances, for this specific manuscript.

– No

Notes: This manuscript is not in a cemetery; others might have been ritualistically buried with their caretakers.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: Manuscripts have not been typically stored in temples in Cham communities.

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: The most common place for storing Cham manuscripts during the 20th century -- and even earlier times -- has been in a small woven basket called a *ciét tapuk*, which can be suspended from the rafters of a traditional home. The advantage to the storage method is that this is the coolest and driest location in the home.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2000 CE

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: This particular manuscript has been held in several libraries/archives, including the (former) Summer Institute of Linguistics (in former Saigon, defunct, no longer exists) and the University of Washington. The Center for Cham Culture also likely has versions of this manuscript, if not exact copies.

↳ Specify

- Specify: The library version of the manuscript circulates to other libraries through the Inter-Library Loan network.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: The ciét tapuk itself is not typically accompanied by iconography or images. Instead, it is a rather simple basket.

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– At home

Notes: If any iconography is present in the context of the ciét tapuk, it is most often on the manuscripts themselves.

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The most common religious symbol in the Cham community that could be argued to be "an icon" is the "homkar." Similar to the Hindu "om" symbol at its core, the homkar also adds elements to represent life and death, the sun and the moon, along with the Ahiér (Hindu) and Awal (Muslim) elements of the cosmos. Some individuals might have this symbol on their bodies in the form of a tattoo. It commonly appears on manuscripts, although it does not appear on the specific manuscript in question for this entry.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The Republic of Vietnam, the relevant government in question, did not support this text. However, the production of the version of the text referenced by this entry was through programs that would have had to secure government approval.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Although there are versions of the Sakawi Cam (Cham calendar) that could be considered as

"official" in more contemporary Cham communities, this text does not represent an official religious manuscript.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Notes: The archaic ritual language for Cham manuscripts tends to be written in Akhar Rik script. No Akhar Rik script is observed on this manuscript.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Cham language is considered endogenous.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Loan words from Arabic and Sanskrit are considered exogenous.

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: The blend of Sanskrit, Arabic and Cham languages is considered as an important symbolic construction of how the cosmos actually are formed, exist, and understood.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The language of written modern Cham is conveyed in Akhar Thrah script. Literacy in this script was historically low during the period in question, and mostly confined to religious specialists. The script went through a revival period, beginning with the period in question, and literacy in the script then increased.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

- Divinity
- Institutions

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

- Yes

Notes: Both the Summer Institute of Linguistics and the Center for Cham Culture supported teacher training and the script's promotion through the 1970s. By the late 1970s and 1980s, only the Center for Cham Culture was directly involved in supporting the teaching of the script, as the SIL no longer operated in Vietnam after the fall of Saigon.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

- Yes

Notes: Arguably romanized Cham is non-religious, since it was not created by members of the Cham community and is not imbued with any particularly symbolic meaning (unlike, say, Akhar Thrah or Akhar Rik script).

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

- Yes

Notes: Oral traditions have been commonly used to support the study of Cham manuscripts, especially the Cham calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2023 CE

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

- Field doesn't know

Notes: It's not ever clear who precisely Sakawi Cam texts are intended for. This one is a general text, but only 10% of the population at the time could hope to read it. Is the audience the entire community? Or just the readership? We cannot determine based on the content of this manuscript itself.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

- No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Especially in the mid to late 1960s, a distinct element of reformist Islam entered Vietnam via Cambodia and Malaysia. After being involved with the founding the Vietnam Association of Cham Islam in the early 1960s, islami reformists approached Bani (Awal) communities in the south-central coastal region. They attempted to get them to become more "mainstream." Although some members of the Cham Bani community accepted this invitation, most rejected it. Ahier-Awal manuscripts expressing Bani and Ahier unity became more important in this context, consequently also elevating the importance of the Sakawi Cam calendar.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The text describes the appropriate time of year for high holidays and life cycle rituals.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 50

Notes: The ritual of Suk Yeng -- a gathering of religious dignitaries -- has emerged to determine and systematize the Cham calendar over time. It is not clear when the ritual of Suk Yeng began.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2023 CE

↳ How often do the rituals take place?
– Specify: All rituals in the calendar occur every year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Yes
Notes: The Sakawi Cam itself is an orthopraxy check, as it specifies the appropriate times for ritual behavior.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?
– Yes
Notes: Although the text itself is designed to prevent holidays and life cycle rituals from distinct religious communities from overlapping and therefore, causing intra-family conflict, it does imply that certain practices engaged in for these holidays can occur synchronically. For instance, during the Kate holiday, events occur at multiple temple-tower complexes, shrines, and smaller temples.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
– Yes

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Arguably "calendars" are their own category of text.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Solar?

– Luni-solar? (Combined, as in Mayan, Javanese, or Cham calendars)

– Duodenary?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– Yes

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– Yes

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– Yes

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– Yes

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: Annual

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

–All members

–Elites

–Non-elites

–Only locals

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Festivals typically only have participation from members of a specific half of Cham society as core participants: either Ahier or Awal/Bani. That said, local elites and foreigners have attended these festivals, including Vietnamese tourists. This is especially true for Katé.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

–number: 2000

Notes: This number is an educated guess for attendance of Katé.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– Yes

Notes: During elements of certain holidays, spiritual elect eat first. For instance, during Ramâwan (Ramadan) members of the Bani cleric class (Awal) eat first. A similar practice exists for monastics involved in ceremonies in nearby Buddhist communities and the Cham Ahiér community as well.

↳ Pilgramages?

– No

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: Temple tower complexes and Bani grave sites, as implied through the ritual use of the word "Mbeng" or "to consume/eat/feast" in reference to those holidays.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– Yes

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– Yes

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Ahier community members may be cremated. Members of very traditional communities (Cam Jat) may participate in "reburial" rituals including a second burial.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?
– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?
– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?
– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?
– Yes

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– No

Notes: Although common in Cham religious contexts, the text does not specify.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: Although common in Cham religious contexts, the text does not specify.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: Although common in Cham religious contexts, the text does not specify.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: Division of cosmos between Ahiér (Hindu) and Awal (Muslim) elements.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Text does not specify.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Text does not specify.

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Text does not specify.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Although not explicitly mentioned, jin (from Arabic: djinn) are present in the Bani cosmos.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: In that many are women, yes. However, the text does not make this clear.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: All are ethnic Cham.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?

– Yes

Notes: They become part of a de facto class of ritual practitioners subordinate to the spiritual elect, although some may indeed be members of the spiritual elect.

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required?

– No

Notes: For members of the Ahier community they are not required but socially encouraged. For members of the Bani community, they are socially discouraged from alcohol.

↳ Is physical ordeal required?

– Yes

Notes: Based off of anthropological evidence, yes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1835 CE - 2023 CE

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not imply this, and so the field cannot know based on the text. However, there is anthropological evidence of all of the above.

↳ Wild animals?

– Yes

↳ Domesticated animals?

– Yes

↳ Captive animals?

– Yes

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Smoke

↳ Other form of divination:

– Specify: Through stars.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: Although present in anthropological evidence, the text does not specify.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Although present in anthropological evidence, the text does not specify.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Although present in anthropological evidence, the text does not specify.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– No
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– No

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Purity/ritual purity

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 4

Notes: At the very most frequent, rituals would be 4 hours apart. However, most rituals would be only once or twice a day, or even more commonly, only once or twice a week. Still, many members of the community have only participated during such rituals around the time of the high holidays.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The statistical variance in size makes this number difficult to accurately assess. Some may be a few as 50 people. Others may be as many as tens of thousands, depending on how you define the ritual itself.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Text does not imply or specify.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– Yes

Notes: Even members of the Bani community who do not drink may use tobacco or chew betel.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: The text implies such sacrifices and states they exist for certain high holidays, but does not specify anything about such sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of sacred space, beyond, say "washing."

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Notes: It would be best to describe the entire Cham community (both Ahiér and Awal elements) as a "faith elect" given the above list.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: Traditionally, only priests and clerics have produced Sakawi Cam texts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2023 CE

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: There are not.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Socially, the redistribution of food during high holidays is the most explicit form of social welfare referenced by the text.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: This is implied in the sense that most literate members of Cham communities were male priests or clerics. However, there are records of women who have either been involved with the education about the larger textual tradition or been masters of it.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: A traditional student(anak seh)-teacher(po gru) relationship is 1:1, although larger groups of students are referenced by other texts in this tradition.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Most importantly, the text specifies the times that public works are used for ritual action.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The text specifies the proper time for the use of water management for organized irrigation and timing of rituals associated with both planting and harvest of rice.